

LISTENING AND TEACHING STYLES TOWARDS CREATING STRATEGIC INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIAL

Marimel M. Pagcaliwagan, MAEd

*San Agustin Integrated School, Ibaan Sub-office, Division of Batangas Province, Philippines
Graduate School, Philippine Christian University, Manila, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10102187>

ABSTRACT

Language is an integral aspect of communication in our daily lives. It is mainly through listening that language learners are exposed to a new language that needs and enhances the development of their overall second- or foreign-language skills. This study aimed to determine the significant relationship between the students' listening styles and the English language teachers' teaching styles. It utilized a descriptive research design with 70 Grade 10 public school English teachers in Congressional District 4, Batangas Province. The research employed a total sampling technique and collected data through a researcher-constructed questionnaire and focus group discussion guide. Data analysis relied on means, standard deviations, and Pearson's Moment of Correlation. The results indicate a significant relationship between students' listening styles and teachers' teaching styles. Task-oriented is the preferred listening style of the students. People who listen in a relational or analytical listening style came in second and third, respectively, with critical listening having the least value. On the other hand, the most used teaching style was facilitator, while lecturer came in second. Delegator and hybrid teaching styles came after it, with demonstrator being the least prevalent. Notable issues and challenges that impede English language teachers' teaching of listening skills include linguistic issues such as a lack of vocabulary and pronunciation, alongside non-linguistic concerns like learning materials, classroom environment, and teachers' time and training. The proposed strategic instructional materials consist of adaptable worksheets and guided activities, aiming to enhance students' listening skills and practical application of new knowledge acquired in the classroom.

Keywords: *listening styles; teaching styles; strategic instructional material; issues; challenges*

INTRODUCTION

Listening is an important English skill that needs to be worked on. This has been seen as a strong foundation that can help develop the students' minds further to learn more. This depends on how well the learner understands what the speaker is saying. It is the first language that students learn to build a solid academic foundation and improve their thinking skills, and it is an important part of how people communicate for the rest of their lives. This means being able to understand a speaker's accent or pronunciation as well as his or her grammar, vocabulary, and meaning.

Despite their significance, listening skills are taught passively or not at all in classrooms (Okume, 2019). This has raised concerns among language experts and researchers because they know that getting learners to be active listeners by using best practices in education is a way to help them do well in English and other school subjects. As described in the K–12 toolkit of the Department of Education (2012), Integrated Language Arts Education at high school focuses more on reading comprehension of various texts, writing and composition, research, and learning techniques, all of which encourage critical and creative thinking, while listening is less focused. In certain situations, when the teacher is busy trying to relate their known experiences to the unknown, these students may have drifted in thought.

The significance of listening comprehension in language instruction has consistently been emphasized, although numerous educators fail to allocate adequate attention to it within the classroom setting (Gilakjani & Sabouri, 2016). It could be noted that the Philippines attained the lowest score in reading and the second lowest score in Mathematics and Science among the 79 countries that participated in the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) findings. The findings are quite alarming and possess the capacity to exert a substantial influence on the educational system of the country. To achieve greater academic success, it is imperative for students to possess good listening skills, a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter, critical thinking abilities, and an appreciation for the material.

As is evident from the literature review, efforts have been made by several researchers to improve the listening skills of students. However, further research is required to investigate the learners' own perceptions of their listening experience, as listening cannot be clearly examined and accurately described. Learners' perceptions regarding their listening styles may provide clues as to the sources of difficulties—how or why understanding breaks down—and the strategies that could be used by teachers to overcome issues and challenges.

In relation to it, listening styles play a significant role in learners' lives considering what has been addressed so far. If students recognize their own listening style, they will be able to integrate it into their learning process. Teachers will seek to adjust their teaching styles to adapt to the listening styles of learners. Future researchers should continue to address this topic by providing participants with various circumstances in which certain styles will be preferred over others. The degree to which listeners who may prefer a specific style are able to adjust to the needs of the conversation It would be important to understand how people identify the key features of the situation that help listeners determine which style to use, to understand which groups of people are better able to match the proper style to their own listening needs, and to explore how listeners deal with situations that require a style in which they are not competent, to name a few research questions (Bodie, 2010; Bodie, Denham, & Gearhart, 2013; Gearhart, Bodie, & Worthington, 2014; Salazar, 2017).

On the other hand, it is a fact that both teachers and students vary in style. Teaching styles, then, are likely to be quite different among teachers (Anggriani and Nurrohmah, 2018; La'biran, 2017; Abbas and Hussain, 2018). Students, of course, vary in their preferred methods of learning, particularly in listening. It is important that teachers are flexible, and there must be a desire to analyze what is happening in the classroom environment. Students can benefit from having teachers who teach in different ways because this can help them become successful listeners and be able to work with and communicate with a variety of people. Teachers must plan a range of teaching styles for the students to understand and respond effectively to the requirements of the classroom and program (Ridwan, Sutresna, and Haryeti, 2019). The findings indicate that English learners at the secondary level want to experience their freedom in the classroom, accompanied by a scheduled lecture or a combination of both types, so teachers should accommodate both student-centered and teacher-centered approaches in teaching.

Meanwhile, it is clear from the literature study that the problems and challenges a teacher faces that have been identified take on different forms in linguistic and non-linguistic settings. Problems with pronunciation, insufficient vocabulary, and a lack of background information are the most frequently experienced difficulties with the language. Because of their limited English language skills and knowledge base, students often struggle to follow classroom discussions and lectures. Consequently, learners face challenges not only in comprehending the text but also in pronouncing it correctly. There is a lack of materials for educators to employ when teaching listening skills that are not directly related to language. Teachers can help students understand by giving them the right materials and activities, giving them enough time to finish their goals, and keeping the listening environment convenient (Coskun and Kopru, 2021; Alrawashdeh and Al-zayed, 2017; Tersta and Novianti, 2017; Haji and Saaed, 2022; Cole, 2018; Lestari et al., 2021; Sah and Shah, 2020).

Additionally, teachers must create teaching materials. Teachers can help learners improve their knowledge by equipping them with the skill of listening, allowing them to be successful learners. As educators prepare their own teaching materials, they can create ample information in terms of concepts and subject knowledge. It would be easier for students to learn in an acceptable way. It is important to make changes to materials to improve them or make them more suitable for a particular type of learner. Materials designed to be used individually by learners on their own or without access to a teacher or classroom may be of great benefit to the learners (Kapur, 2019; Kumar and Shankar, 2021).

In this sense, strategic instructional materials have the advantage of representing and encouraging the background and needs of learners. It can promote learning among students and increase their success. For example, worksheets and guided exercises adapted to students' listening styles as the output of the study may provide an important opportunity for a student to practice a new skill acquired in class. These teaching materials are helpful in the learning process because they encourage the student to individually analyze the information and provide repetition. Teacher-made materials, no matter what kind of material, allow teachers to modify tasks that will activate the listening style of each student (Putri and Refnaldi, 2020; Furwani and Andi, 2020; Sarmiento, 2018; Unver, 2017; Alabere, 2016; Cahn and Renandya, 2016).

Considering this, it is essential to determine the listening styles of learners prior to comprehending the challenges of teaching listening. Nevertheless, it is evident that focusing on a particular listening style might be detrimental to success. Listening will continue to be a problem if students are unable to appreciate what listening is and what its structure demands, as well as if they are unable to comprehend their own unique listening styles and discover strategies to

improve their listening skills. If English language teachers know what kind of listeners their students are, they can figure out why they can't remember certain facts and why they don't like certain speakers or topics.

It is therefore the purpose of this study to help teachers in such a way that they will have a better understanding of their teaching styles as well as their students' listening styles. It will encourage learners to listen in class in an engaged and successful way. They can use listening styles to improve their abilities to trigger the right response from people they collaborate with. It can give them insights into the gaps that may exist as well as into where they typically focus. As this happens, learners' academic success will improve not only in English but in all other subjects. Through this, the researcher would be able to determine the expectations of the students about their own listening styles.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the listening style of Grade 10 students in Congressional District 4 of the Division of Batangas Province with the English teachers' style of teaching.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the students' listening style relative to the following:
 - 1.1 relational
 - 1.2 analytical
 - 1.3 task-oriented
 - 1.4 critical
2. What is the teaching style of English language teachers relative to the following:
 - 2.1 lecturer
 - 2.2 demonstrator
 - 2.3 facilitator
 - 2.4 delegator
 - 2.5 hybrid
3. Is there any significant relationship between the students' listening style and the teachers' teaching style?
4. What are the issues and challenges encountered by teachers in making students listen in class?
5. What strategic instructional material may be proposed that is adapted to the students' listening styles?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive research design to evaluate and interpret the data acquired during the research period. The method of descriptive research goes beyond data collection and tabulation. According to Siedlecki (2020), the objective of a descriptive study is to adequately describe the events in their natural contexts. This type of research design prohibits the researcher from manipulating the variables; instead, it merely describes them and the sample. The study used a researcher-constructed questionnaire and a focus group discussion guide as gathering instruments. The questionnaire consists of two parts. The first part is modified from a standard questionnaire to fit the requirements of the study, while the other is a researcher-made questionnaire. The researcher herself created it because of readings from related literature. Another data collection tool used in this study is the Focus Group Discussion Guide. It is meant

for English language teachers to express their thoughts and for the researcher to learn about subjects and activities for strategic instructional content matched to students' listening habits. The researcher's instrument made use of the Likert scale to determine the assessment of the respondents' listening styles and the English language teachers' teaching styles. Means (M), standard deviations (SD), and Pearson's r Moment of Correlation were used as statistical tools to analyze the data. The study included a total population of 70 Grade 10 public school English language teachers from Batangas' Congressional District 4. The study participants were selected via total sampling.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the results regarding the Grade 10 students' listening styles and their English teachers' teaching styles, its relationships, as well as the issues and challenges encountered by teachers in teaching listening.

1. Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment of students' listening styles.

1.1 Relational

Table 1

Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment of students' listening style in terms of Relational

When listening in an English class, the students...	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
1. are concerned with how the speaker feels in a narrative.	3.21	0.58	ME
2. enjoy the emotional complexities in a story because it helps them to communicate in English.	3.24	0.57	ME
3. use personal experiences to grasp the speaker's feelings and mood.	3.38	0.57	ME
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.28	0.47	ME

1.2 Analytical

Table 2

Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment of students' listening style in terms of Analytical

When listening in an English class, the students...	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
1. tend to wait before passing judgment on information gained from news stories, speeches, thought-provoking debates, and panel discussions.	3.17	0.60	ME
2. consider all sides of the matter in an audio composition before they respond.	3.04	0.65	ME
3. concentrate on what the speaker has to say to learn new ideas before forming any opinions.	3.32	0.62	ME
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.18	0.51	ME

1.3 Task-oriented

Table 3
Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment of students' listening style in terms of Task-oriented

When listening in an English class, the students...	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
1. prefer information that is well-organized, precise, and accurate to complete the task quickly.	3.35	0.59	ME
2. ask questions for elaboration when important ideas are unclear and not present.	3.26	0.64	ME
3. pay particular attention to facts and concepts related to the task at hand.	3.28	0.58	ME
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.30	0.48	ME

1.4 Critical

Table 4
Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment of students' listening style in terms of Critical

When listening in an English class, the students...	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
1. search for grammar errors in analyzing listening texts based on factors such as fluency, sound, cohesion, and correctness.	2.95	0.60	ME
2. find inconsistencies in speakers' logic in interviews, advertisements, political statements, and other claims.	2.86	0.69	ME
3. recognize the main points of messages and take notes that accurately represent the speaker's intended meanings.	3.23	0.59	ME
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.01	0.54	ME

2. Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment on teaching styles.

2.1 Lecturer

Table 5
Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment on teaching styles in terms of Lecturer

When teaching students, I...	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
1. provide specific instructions on how I want the listening task to be done.	3.82	0.39	GE
2. give a lecture on the assigned topic while they take notes and memorize key pieces of information.	3.61	0.58	GE
3. review the listening material and give feedback on student's performance in the form of observations and suggestions.	3.65	0.48	GE
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.69	0.39	GE

2.2 Facilitator

Table 6
Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment on teaching styles in terms of Facilitator

When teaching students, I...	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
1. develop listening activities that inspire them to take action and to be accountable for their learning.	3.61	0.49	GE
2. encourage them to create their own ideas on the given topic as they listen.	3.80	0.40	GE
3. ask questions and suggest ways of doing the listening task.	3.77	0.46	GE
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.72	0.36	GE

2.3 Delegator

Table 7
Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment on teaching styles in terms of Delegator

When teaching students, I...	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
1. assign roles and duties to learners in class.	3.70	0.46	GE
2. serve as a mentor enabling them to plan and execute their own listening tasks.	3.66	0.49	GE
3. show what they can do when working in a group or independently on a topic that's important to them.	3.64	0.51	GE
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.67	0.40	GE

2.4 Hybrid

Table 8
Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment on teaching styles in terms of Hybrid

When teaching students, I...	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
1. allow them to make choices between listening activities.	3.58	0.59	GE
2. share my knowledge and expertise as they listen for them to be well prepared for further tasks in the future.	3.77	0.42	GE
3. incorporate personal preferences and specific interests to make listening experiences more enjoyable for them.	3.67	0.49	GE
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.67	0.40	GE

2.5 Demonstrator

Table 9
Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment of teaching styles in terms of Demonstrator

When teaching students, I...	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
1. instruct them to listen for the gist, specific information, and speaker's attitude or opinion to master the listening material.	3.73	0.44	GE

2. extend how different principles and concepts can be applied.	3.52	0.53	GE
3. conduct a small group discussion in English class to help students improve their listening skills.	3.57	0.51	GE
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.61	0.41	GE

3. Relationship between the Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment of students' listening styles and teachers' teaching styles.

Table 10

Relationship between the Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment of students' listening styles in terms of Relational and the teachers' teaching styles

	R-value	R²-value	p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Lecturer	0.24	0.0576	0.006	Reject Ho	Significant
Facilitator	0.331	0.1096	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Delegator	0.349	0.1218	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Hybrid	0.333	0.1109	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Demonstrator	0.357	0.1274	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 11

Relationship between the Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment of students' listening styles in terms of Analytical and the teachers' teaching styles

	R-value	R²-value	p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Lecturer	0.223	0.050	0.010	Reject Ho	Significant
Facilitator	0.331	0.110	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Delegator	0.355	0.126	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Hybrid	0.258	0.067	0.003	Reject Ho	Significant
Demonstrator	0.373	0.139	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 12

Relationship between the Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment of students' listening styles in terms of Task-oriented and the teachers' teaching styles

	R-value	R²-value	p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Lecturer	0.299	0.089	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Facilitator	0.297	0.088	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Delegator	0.368	0.135	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Hybrid	0.307	0.094	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Demonstrator	0.35	0.123	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 13
Relationship between the Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment of students' listening styles in terms of Critical and the teachers' teaching styles

	R-value	R²-value	p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Lecturer	0.288	0.083	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Facilitator	0.359	0.129	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Delegator	0.334	0.112	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Hybrid	0.343	0.118	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Demonstrator	0.348	0.121	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

4. Issues and challenges encountered by teachers in making students listen in class.

Table 14

Student-related issues and challenges	N
distracted by environmental noises	6
ignoring listening activities	1
insufficient familiarity with the pronunciation	7
lack of awareness on the listening material	3
limited vocabulary	8
listening without interest	1
not adhering to listening guidelines	2

Table 15

Administrative-related issues and challenges	N
greater amount of time is devoted to group discussion	1
insufficient time for listening activities	7
lack of available time for listening instruction	8
less time devoted to discussing questions and answers	2
more time is spent clarifying listening rules before the activity	1
too much administrative work consumes instructional time	1
unfixed schedule for delivering instruction	6

Table 16

Resource-related issues and challenges	N
lack of speakers, computers, and monitors in the classroom	7
insufficient use of teaching materials and media	6
necessity to enhance the content included in the book	5
responsibility to produce listening content for learners	6
limited resources on listening tactics	3
listening exercises fails to engage learners' interest	1
provided listening resources do not align with the learners' level of complexity	1

Table 17

Teacher-related issues and challenges	N
absence of training courses primarily designed to enhance listening skills	7
difficulty with listening comprehension teaching methods	3
inability to impart verbal messages to students	1
insufficient expertise on teaching listening	6
lack of motivation	1
lack of special training on how to teach listening skills	8
struggling to impart the skills necessary for listening comprehension	1

DISCUSSION

Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment of students' listening styles.

As can be gleaned in Table 1, the respondents assessed the relational listening style of learners with a Moderate Extent which got a composite mean of 3.28. The indicator, 'use personal experiences to grasp the speaker's feelings and mood' had the greatest mean under the Relational Listening Style (mean=3.38). It demonstrates how the learners deal with knowledge, actions, events, and experiences as they verbalize them to demonstrate their interest while listening to the speakers. Reflecting on content helped to focus on the issue, but it is also necessary to reflect on the sentiments and emotions communicated to completely comprehend the message. On the contrary, the indicator, 'enjoy the emotional complexities in a story because it helps them to communicate in English' came in second while the indicator, 'concerned with how the speaker feels in a narrative' is the least favored used by students in the Relational listening Style.

This suggests that the learners prefer to connect the speakers with emotional components. Relational listening gets students to actively think about what the speaker is saying and what it means. By showing empathy, respect, and a genuine interest in what others have to say, students create a positive and supportive environment for successful communication. In the same way, learners can improve their verbal and unconscious communication skills by learning to listen relationally. They know how to say what they think, ask good questions, and have talks that matter. Also, they become more aware of their facial cues, which can help them communicate better with other people. The results shown align with the conclusions drawn by Nemec et al. (2017), suggesting that actual performances have the capacity to elicit sincere emotions derived from genuine interactions, hence enhancing learners' active involvement in the process of listening and speaking. The process of turn-taking, the exchange of feedback between the speaker and listener, and the potential inclusion of a peer observer facilitate the individual learner's reflection and the development of a more profound understanding of their relational dynamics in conversation beyond the mere performance of specific behaviors.

Regarding the analytical listening style in Table 2, the data indicates that respondents rated it as Moderate Extent, which got a composite mean of 3.18. The indicator, 'learners concentrate on what the speaker has to say to acquire new ideas before forming opinions' received the highest mean score of 3.32, followed by the indicator, 'tend to wait before passing judgment on information gained from news stories, speeches, thought-provoking debates, and panel discussions. In contrast, the indicator, 'consider all aspects of an issue before responding in an

audio composition' had the lowest mean score of 3.04. It simply implies that analytical listening allows students to actively connect with the language and its intricacies in an English classroom. They focus on vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, sentence structures, intonation, and other language characteristics. This concentrated attention to language components improves their overall language ability and further expands their vocabulary and grammar skills.

These findings are consistent with those of Mulder (2019), who noted that analytical listening supports conversational balance and unbiased information processing. Feelings matter a lot while talking to other people. Whenever there is a positive conversational mood, objectivity tends to fade into the background. By being aware of this, one can strike a balance between their emotions and their logical thinking. After conducting a cause-and-effect analysis, it is possible to identify a problem's effects more accurately as well. An analytical listener has the capacity to examine aspects of an issue objectively and apply models to them. The analytical listener can get a lot of information and then research it by separating primary difficulties from partial ones. The analytical listener will be in a far better position to draw logical conclusions, identify the true cause, and come up with appropriate solutions after gathering all the evidence.

As depicted in Table 3, the respondents assessed the task-oriented listening style to a Moderate Extent, with a composite mean of 3.30. The indicator 'prefer information that is well-organized, precise, and accurate to complete the task quickly' had the greatest mean of 3.35 while the indicator, 'pay particular attention to facts and concepts related to the task at hand' came in second. It implies that they like to comprehend the message's content immediately, and disorganization frustrates them because it hinders them from doing an action. With a mean of 3.26, the indicator, 'ask questions for elaboration when important ideas are unclear and not present' was identified as the least favored, which implies that when they listen to the speaker, they pay attention to how reliable and accurate the content is. The main concerns of task-oriented listeners include finding certain information or achieving a particular goal. Before anything else, they concentrate on the key ideas, knowledge, and guidelines required to accomplish their objectives. Second, they focus just on the crucial facts and ignore irrelevant information. Third, they tend to react fast and act following the points. Finally, they take the initiative to ask questions pertinent to the subject and actively seek clarification.

The results suggest that task-oriented listening allows students to connect their behaviors with the desired outcomes or expectations. They can ensure that their work satisfies the requirements and contributes to the broader objectives by focusing on the task and actively listening to instructions. Additionally, it offers opportunities for continuous learning and development. Individuals can absorb new information, obtain insights, and advance their knowledge and abilities through active listening. This listening style encourages individuals to remain receptive to new ideas and perspectives. Ostad, et al. (2018), who investigated the effect of task-based listening activities on students' listening comprehension, supported these findings. According to him, task-based activities can increase student engagement and add variety to the classroom. Using tasks to give students a sense of purpose and, consequently, encourage them to interact with one another more was cited as an effective method of teaching English. Several studies indicate that tasks can significantly impact learning and pedagogy: thus, using tasks benefits teaching and learning.

As shown in Table 4, the respondents assessed the critical listening style as moderate extent with a composite mean of 3.01. The indicator, 'recognize the main points of messages and take notes that accurately represent the speaker's intended meanings' had the highest mean of 3.23.

It suggests that students like listening to and noting key concepts, evaluating the content's strengths and flaws, and then synthesizing and evaluating what they have learned. Meanwhile, the indicator, 'search for grammar errors in analyzing listening texts based on factors such as fluency, sound, cohesion, and correctness' came in second. On the other hand, with a mean of 2.86, the item 'find inconsistencies in speakers' logic in interviews, advertisements, political statements, and other claims' was identified as the least favored strategy which indicates that when learners listen, it is unlikely that they will pay consideration to logical errors and inconsistencies in what is being said. Critical listening entails paying close attention to comprehending the message, judging its veracity, seeing any logical flaws or fallacies, and analyzing the facts or arguments. Individuals who use a critical listening approach can improve their ability to analyze information objectively, make informed decisions, and engage in meaningful dialogues. It is a valuable talent in various situations, including academic settings, professional settings, and everyday interactions where analytical thinking is required.

The above results conform with Wuryaningrum, et al. (2022), who indicated that critical listening could foster a disposition toward critical thinking. It happens because critical listening activities, namely using common sense, understanding fact and opinion information, minimizing assumptions, and being open to new ideas, are crucial to disposition. Critical listening is a matter of strengthening critical thinking skills from what is being listened to. Therefore, the critical listening problem is a problem for all students in all subject cases. In the English language subject, critical listening creates good communication patterns in conveying ideas from what is being listened to.

To sum up, based on the values presented, task-oriented listening is the students' preferred listening style. People who listen in a way that is relational or analytical came in second and third, with critical having the least value. Under critical, the spread of the standard deviation shows that this is true. This is because critical has the largest Sd value. This means that, based on what they said, students have a wide range of views.

Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment on teaching styles.

It can be gleaned from Table 5 that the respondents assessed Lecturer teaching styles as great extent with a composite mean of 3.69. The indicator, 'provide specific instructions on how I want the listening task to be done' has the highest mean (3.82). Meanwhile, the indicator, 'review the listening material and give feedback on student's performance in the form of observations and suggestions' came in second with a mean of 3.65 and the indicator, 'give a lecture on the assigned topic while they take notes and memorize key pieces of information' yields the lowest mean (3.61). The findings show that English language teachers clarify what their students should do, offer clear directions, and give meaningful feedback to the learners. Teachers are also responsible for preparing the listening lesson and providing guidance to their students.

As revealed from the results, a lecturer's teaching style can benefit the speaker's credibility and the audience's perception of their knowledge. If a listener believes that the lecturer is informed and trustworthy, they are more likely to pay attention and become engaged with the presented content. It has the potential to cultivate trust and produce an atmosphere conducive to learning. Additionally, they can set standards and expectations for behavior, ensuring that students remain focused throughout the lecture and actively listen. It can prevent distractions and provide an environment that is favorable to learning. These results are consistent with Thi and Nguyen's (2021) findings that the lecturer's or authoritative teaching style is the most positively influential

factor on students' learning motivation. This style significantly motivates students to learn the subject, mainly when teachers deliver lessons with a fluent and modulated voice.

Along with Facilitator as a variable of teaching styles in Table 6, English language teachers mostly perceive this, as shown in the overall mean of 3.72. The highest mean of 3.80 is noted in the indicator, "When teaching students, I encourage them to create their ideas on the given topic as they listen". Meanwhile, the indicator, 'ask questions and suggest ways of doing the listening task,' came in second. On the contrary, "develop listening activities that inspire them to take action and to be accountable for their learning" obtained the lowest mean of 3.61. These indicators of Facilitator teaching styles were identified based on the English language teachers' assessments. The findings suggest that teachers encourage learners to generate and respond to their ideas. Likewise, it enables students to actively participate in listening by providing them with various settings and opportunities.

These results align with the conclusions drawn by Anggraeni and Yusnita (2017), who assert that in addressing the difficulties of the 21st century pertaining to the responsibilities of educators, it becomes evident that the primary function of teachers is that of facilitators. Hence, student-centered learning is the approach that empowers educators to fulfill their responsibilities. The role of instructors is to serve as facilitators who promote the development of critical thinking, creativity, and independence among students. Educators actively engage students in the process of planning both the learning activities and assessments that align with their preferred styles.

In terms of the Delegator teaching style in Table 7, the respondents assessed it to a great extent, with a composite mean of 3.67. The indicator obtaining the highest mean of (3.70) is 'When teaching students, I assign roles and duties to learners in class.' The second is 'serve as a mentor enabling them to plan and execute their listening tasks' with a mean of 3.66. The lowest mean (3.64) along Delegator is in the indicator, 'When teaching students, I show what they can do when working by group or independently on a topic that is important to them.' From the findings, English language teachers assign responsibility to the learners and hold them accountable for their involvement. Students can acquire a wide range of abilities and participate in activities that allow them to study areas of interest as they take on diverse responsibilities.

These results conform with La'biran and Dewi's (2021) observation that the teacher helped the students learn through conversation. So, the activities in class helped students come up with their ideas about the subject matter by getting them to answer questions well and give their views through the exercises the teacher provided. The teacher then gave each student a question to help them develop more ways to learn independently. The teacher reviewed the most critical parts of the information, and then learners asked questions about themselves. Students were free to answer questions from the teacher because they were relevant. Likewise, the student paid attention to what the teacher said in the classroom.

Meanwhile, as shown in Table 8, the respondents assessed the hybrid teaching style to a great extent, with a composite mean of 3.67. The indicator with the highest mean of 3.77 in the Hybrid teaching style is "when teaching students, I share my knowledge and expertise as they listen for them to be well prepared for further tasks in the future'. English language teachers regard this as being, to a great extent. Meanwhile, the indicator, 'incorporate personal preferences and specific interests to make listening experiences more enjoyable for them' came in second, and the indicator, "When teaching students, I allow them to make choices between listening activities" has the lowest mean of 3.58. It suggests that English language teachers are attempting to

integrate new developing pedagogies and learning theories, as well as the new challenging responsibilities of students and teachers in obtaining knowledge and interpreting it, particularly in listening. With hybrid teaching, students can receive individualized training. Teachers can tailor listening materials to different skill levels or learning goals. They can also offer specialized education or help one-on-one or in small groups. It fosters collaboration and feedback. Students can record analysis, debate comprehension, and listen together. Online classes allow contact and feedback outside of class, enabling continued learning and engagement.

The above results support the findings of Mazloom and Hussain (2020), who investigated the teaching styles of secondary-level English teachers. Teachers of English employed a variety of teaching styles, including expert, facilitator, personal model, delegator, and formal authority, to varying degrees. In addition, teachers utilized a variety of instructional methods in their classrooms. These findings also support the present research's concept that a teacher does not rely on a single teaching style pattern. They can employ a teaching style that combines various other teaching styles. Their present study also investigated the variety of primary and secondary teaching styles adopted by secondary-level English instructors. The results indicated that English teachers employed a blend of teaching styles to varying degrees.

On the other hand, as seen in Table 9, the respondents assessed the demonstrator's teaching style to a great extent, with a composite mean of 3.61. The indicator with the highest mean of 3.73 in Demonstrator teaching style is "When teaching students, I instruct them to listen for the gist, specific information, and speaker's attitude or opinion to master the listening material." The second is "When teaching students, conduct a small group discussion in English class to help students improve their listening skills, with a mean of 3.57. The indicator, "When teaching students, I extend how different principles and concepts can be applied" has the lowest mean of 3.52. It suggests that English language teachers focus on presenting specific parts of challenging listening ideas to students and, most importantly, serve as the basis for class discussion. Their explanations provide sufficient facts for students to understand what happened and why and the springboard for additional questions by those needing more in-depth knowledge.

These findings supported the study of Khoirunnisa (2023), who found that, of the five styles, the personal model or demonstrator teaching style was one of the most popular and commonly used. Teachers favor defining what and how students must learn. One of the concepts includes the personal behavior of a teacher and how the teacher uses instructional materials to transmit or receive data representing knowledge from students. As a result, most students are likelier to be engaged in the lesson when the teacher employs the demonstrator teaching style.

With the above results of the teaching styles of the Grade 10 English language teachers, the table revealed that the most used teaching type was Facilitator. In contrast, the second most widely used teaching style was Lecturer. The third most popular teaching styles were Delegator and Hybrid. In comparison, Demonstrator is the least dominant. The table shows that Facilitator was the most used teaching style, with an overall mean of 3.72, while Demonstrator was the least frequently used teaching style, with an overall mean of 3.61. The findings imply that English language teachers assume the role of Facilitator of learning because they provide students with opportunities and activities that enhance their students' initiative and creativity.

Relationship between the Grade 10 English language teachers' assessment of students' listening styles and teachers' teaching styles.

Table 10 presents the relationship between the respondents' assessment of students' listening styles in terms of relational and teachers' teaching styles. It can be gleaned from the above table that there is a significant weak positive relationship between relational and the English teachers' teaching styles with a variability of at most 12.74%.

This conforms with the findings of Jimenez (2022), which emphasizes the significance for educators to set a goal of creating a student-centered classroom environment that fosters a sense of inclusivity and value among students. The initial step involves the establishment of interpersonal connections with students, fostering an environment of trust between educators and learners. The researcher discovered that the implementation of relational pedagogy facilitates the establishment of healthy teacher-student interactions, which in turn enhances students' socio-emotional well-being and academic performance. Additionally, it contributes to the cultivation of students' social and self-assurance abilities.

Table 11 presents the relationship between the respondents' assessment of students' listening style in terms of analytical and the teachers' teaching styles. It can be gleaned from the above table that the p-values are all less than 5% level of significance so the relationships between analytical and the teachers' teaching styles are all significant. Analytical listeners like to learn from facts, proof, and logical reasoning. Teachers can appeal to this thinking by giving references, citing sources, and encouraging students to back up their claims with evidence. A good match between a student's analytical listening style and the way a teacher teaches can help a student who prefers to learn analytically.

The findings indicate that using numerous ways, the teacher must help his students go from marginal to analytical listening. As students age, their listening skills improve. When they start school, they pay more attention. These stages can be identified within a single class, regardless of student age. When a teacher begins a lesson, students may be listening marginally or casually. Students are usually at a borderline level of hearing at the beginning of a class since there may be new sounds, meanings, sentence structures, and concepts (Singhal & Vohra, 2011).

Table 12 presents the relationship between the respondents' assessment of students' listening styles in terms of task-oriented and the teachers' teaching styles. It can be gleaned from the above table that p-values are all less than 5% level of significance so the relationships between task-oriented and the teachers' teaching styles are all significant. Teachers of the English language who focus on tasks work well with students who learn best when they are actively engaged in the material. Both strategies prioritize goal-oriented language use in the context of real-world situations. The teacher develops lessons and exercises for attentive participation and creative problem-solving to foster task-oriented listening. These findings supported Aliasin et al.'s (2019) investigation into the relationship between teachers' understanding of task-based language instruction and their dominant teaching style. The results revealed that teachers' comprehension of it is statistically associated with all teaching style components. It also showed that teachers' knowledge of task-based language instruction significantly predicts all teaching style components.

Table 13 presents the relationship between the respondents' assessment of students' listening styles in terms of critical and the teachers' teaching styles. It can be gleaned from the above

table that weak positive relationships have been established by the given values and these were supported by the correlation coefficients and levels of variability not greater than 13%. The teacher's ability to communicate positively affects students' willingness to learn. Critical listening can help develop an aptitude for critical thinking. This is because the components of critical listening activity, including applying common sense, comprehending factual and opinion information, reducing preconceptions, and being receptive to new ideas, all contribute to the development of disposition (Wuryaningrum, Mutiah, & Rijadi, 2022).

With the above results, it is implied that the students' listening styles and English language teachers' teaching styles have a significant relationship with each other. DepEd's K–12 Basic Education Program (2012) in the Philippines provides further support for these findings through its first distinguishing feature and guiding concept. The curriculum exists solely for the benefit of the student. It focuses on the development of the whole person as a learner. When a teacher creates a safe space where students are accepted and encouraged to try new things while being supported when they make errors, they can cultivate a classroom where students thrive. The student is given the freedom to determine his or her own preferences or choices, both in and out of the classroom. Knowing the students' style will help the teacher deliver the lesson so that students can cope easily, make diverse teaching strategies, and lead to their educational achievement.

The results are also in line with the findings of the study by Abbas and Hussain (2018), which concluded that teaching styles represent the traits and techniques used by instructors to direct their classes. It means that teaching style represents the characteristics that support and coordinate the instructional methods, which in turn enhance the learners' capacity to learn and assist the instructor in achieving the desired results. Each teacher employs a unique teaching style or a combination of styles to make their lessons effective and impressive in terms of accomplishing their teaching objectives. These styles distinguish them from one another, allowing each learner in the class to acquire knowledge in an effective manner through exposure to a variety of teaching styles employed by various teachers. In summary, these styles also meet the challenge of individual differences in the classroom by matching students' learning styles, particularly in listening.

Issues and challenges encountered by teachers in making students listen in class.

One of the challenges of teaching English as shown in Table 14 is dealing with students' increasingly limited vocabulary and pronunciation. Many learners appear to have reached a limited vocabulary, even though vocabulary development plays a vital role in boosting the students' level of language proficiency. Understanding the words that makeup spoken language can be challenging for learners because of the differences between the written and spoken forms of language. These are congruent with the studies of Cole (2018); Lestari, et al. (2021); and Sah and Shah, (2020).

Similarly, students' lack of concentration will cause them to be unaware of the material's content. One of the causes of interruptions in students' listening concentration is the location of the class and its physical condition which is near a road or a crowd. Students' focus is on the source of the sound produced, but the subsequent sound of automobiles or people talking or playing music from outside the classroom undoubtedly causes them to lose focus on the main sound to be captured. These are congruent with the studies of Coskun and Kopru (2021); and Haji and Saaed (2022).

Likewise, lack of time presents another issue or challenge when teaching listening in the English classroom as shown in Table 15, since the teacher is only allotted a certain amount of time to teach listening skills. Some of the students find that they have less time and attention to devote to improving their own listening comprehension skills. Learners are unable to make any progress and cannot acquire communication skills if they do not comprehend the material being presented to them. This is congruent with the study of Tersta and Novianti (2017). All teachers agree that time utilized inside the classroom is not sufficient to bring improvement in the listening skill of the students.

Moreover, as shown in Table 16, another issue was the teacher's difficulty in creating material because the school committee did not provide listening-focused instructional materials. Therefore, the teacher should consult other literature or the Internet for information. This challenge is congruent with the study of Bello (2018) and Alrawashdeh and Al-zayed (2017). It concludes that there is a lack of media and other resources present in schools except the textbooks and lesson notes they go with for teaching that can support instruction and improve students' comprehension in the classroom.

Additionally, the English language teachers disclosed that they had not been required to complete any specific training courses in English Language Teaching that concentrated on the application of listening techniques as shown in Table 17. This makes it quite evident that listening is not given the attention it deserves as a valuable skill for the purposes of teaching and learning. The research that Tersta and Novianti (2017) conducted is likewise connected to and congruent with this.

The responses of the teachers clearly indicate that there are many issues and challenges that teachers face in the English classroom. Some of the major issues and challenges that hinder the teaching of listening skills by English language teachers include a variety of linguistic and non-linguistic issues. These linguistic issues are reflected in vocabulary and pronunciation, as represented by stress, intonation, and the sound system. There were also non-linguistic issues, which included the learners' learning materials, classroom environment, and teachers' time and training devoted to English language instruction. Likewise, no systematic approach is adopted by the teachers to improve the listening skills of the students. To help improve the situation, strategic instructional material in the form of worksheets and guided exercises was proposed.

Strategic Instructional Material adapted to students' listening styles.

The proposed strategic instructional material comprises worksheets and guided activities adapted to students' listening styles, which may improve Grade 10 learners' listening skills and a crucial opportunity to practice a new skill learned in class. These teaching resources will help the learning process by encouraging students to analyze information and independently providing repetition. As stated from the results of the study, the listening styles of Grade 10 students and the teaching styles of English language teachers were found to have a significant relationship with each other, where task-oriented is the most dominant listening style used by the students in learning listening and facilitator is the most common teaching style used by English language teachers in teaching listening. Thus, this strategic instructional material is believed to improve the student's listening skills and provide opportunities in the English classroom.

Likewise, this may also respond to the focus points of mastering the content and performance based on Section 5 of RA 10533, which requires educational approaches to be learner-centered,

considering the learners' nature, innate faculties, or abilities, how they learn, developmental stage, multiple intelligences, learning styles, concerns, interests, feelings, home, and educational background in selecting teaching method and technique. (DepEd, 2012).

Furthermore, each activity is integrated with various English language topics to ensure the integration of listening skills and English language teachers may modify it based on the students' learning needs.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Task-oriented was the most dominant listening style used by the students in learning listening. A mismatch between the students' listening styles and the teachers' teaching styles might impede the learning of language skills, particularly in listening.

2. Facilitator was the most dominant teaching style used by English language teachers in teaching listening. Meanwhile, no teacher can employ every teaching style to meet the needs of every unique student. Rather, they must examine how to balance the demands of various students depending on what they are teaching and their students' goals.

3. The listening styles of Grade 10 students and the teaching styles of English language teachers have a significant relationship with each other.

4. Majority of the concerns and challenges encountered in making students listen are related to a lack of prior knowledge of English vocabulary, pronunciation, listening materials, time constraints, lack of training, and physical environments.

5. The strategic instructional material adapted to students' listening styles, particularly worksheets and guided exercises could be of great help to students in improving their listening skills.

Recommendations

As extracted from the conclusions, the following are recommended:

1. The students should be given immediate feedback regarding their outputs in listening tasks so that they would be able to know how to improve them.

2. The school administrators should encourage English language teachers to participate in trainings on new and relevant teaching styles, as well as inspire them to deal with the global and functional trend of teaching listening.

3. The teachers should be aware of the students' potentials and needs to effectively match their preferred methods of instruction with their students' listening styles.

4. The teachers should be open to the challenges that their profession entails, be proud of the important role they play in their students' lives and strive to improve their teaching styles to match the listening styles of their learners to become more efficient and effective teachers.

5. The strategic instructional material adapted to the students' listening styles may be used by the teachers to enhance their students' listening skills.

6. Further research on Grade 10 students' listening styles and English teachers' teaching styles must be conducted to explore listening and teaching styles in greater depth to fully understand the issues and challenges the teachers encounter in making students listen with the end view of providing solutions to it.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher hereby declares her commitment to upholding established ethical norms and principles within the context of her research. These principles include gaining informed permission from participants, safeguarding their privacy and confidentiality, and mitigating potential harm or risks. In addition, the open management of data, the acknowledgment of conflicts of interest, and the precise documentation of results are fundamental elements of ethical research. By adhering to these principles, not only are the rights and well-being of individuals participating upheld, but the overall ethical standing of the scientific community is also preserved. This, in turn, fosters public trust in research and its outcomes.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express her gratitude to various individuals who played crucial roles in the successful completion of the study. First, to God's divine grace and guidance. Second, to all the experts who provided valuable time and guidance throughout the research process, helping to shape the quality of the research paper. Third, the researcher is equally grateful to the secondary schools that participated in the study and the English language teachers who acted as respondents. Lastly, the researcher expresses deep appreciation to her family, special someone, and friends, for providing hope and encouragement during both high and low points of her research journey. The researcher holds great respect and appreciation for everyone mentioned, and their contributions have been invaluable in this endeavour.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, Q., & Hussain, S. (2018). Comparative Study of Teaching Styles of Various School Groups at Secondary Level in District Chiniot of Punjab. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327674629_Comparative_Study_of_Teaching_Styles_of_Various_School_Groups_at_Secondary_Level_in_District_Chiniot_of_Punjab
- Alabere, R. A. (2017). The Importance of Instructional Materials in Teaching English of a Second Language. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*. Retrieved from: [https://www.ijhssi.org/papers/v6\(9\)/Version-3/F0609033644.pdf](https://www.ijhssi.org/papers/v6(9)/Version-3/F0609033644.pdf)
- Aliasin, S.H., Saeedi, Z., & Pineh, A.J., |Wan, P. (Reviewing editor:) (2019) The relationship between EFL teachers' perception of task-based language teaching and their dominant teaching style, *Cogent Education*, 6:1, DOI: 10.1080/2331186X.2019.1589413
- Alrawashdeh, A. I. & Al-zayed, N. N. (2017). Difficulties that english teachers encounter while teaching listening comprehension and their attitudes towards them. *Canadian Center of Science and Education*. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1140047.pdf>
- Anggraeni K. A., & Yusnita R. (2017). Teachers' role in 21st century: Teacher is a facilitator, not a dictator. *LUNAR: Journal of Language and Art*, 1(1). Retrieved from <https://ejournal.unibabwi.ac.id/index.php/lunar/article/view/72>
- Anggriani, A. & Nurrohmah, H. (2018). An analysis of teacher style in teaching English listening. *Professional Journal of English Education*. Retrieved from: <https://journal.ikipsiliwangi.ac.id/index.php/project/article/download/1416/pdf>
- Bello, A. A. (2018). Curriculum implementation: strategies for mounting listening skills among junior secondary school students. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 63-77. Retrieved

from: <https://www.ijopr.com/download/curriculum-implementation-strategies-for-mounting-listening-skills-among-junior-secondary-school-6379.pdf>

- Bodie, G. D. (2010). The Revised Listening Concepts Inventory (LCI-R): Assessing individual and situational differences in the conceptualization of listening. *Imagination, Cognition and Personality*, 30(3), 301–339. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.2190/IC.30.3.f>
- Bodie, G. D., Worthington, D. L., & Gearhart, C. C., (2013): The Listening Styles Profile-Revised (LSP-R): A Scale Revision and Evidence for Validity, *Communication Quarterly*, 61:1, 72-90. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/263247172_The_Listening_Styles_Profile-Revised_LSP-R_A_Scale_Revision_and_Evidence_for_Validity
- Bodie, Graham & Winter, John & Dupuis, Dana & Tompkins, Tom. (2019). The Echo Listening Profile: Initial Validity Evidence for a Measure of Four Listening Habits. *International Journal of Listening*. 34. 1-25. 10.1080/10904018.2019.1611433. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333470898_The_Echo_Listening_Profile_Initial_Validity_Evidence_for_a_Measure_of_Four_Listening_Habits
- Cahn, L. V., & Renandya, W. A. (2016). Teaching Listening in Mixed-Ability Classes. *The European Journal of Applied Linguistics and TEFL*.
Classrooms at Secondary Level. *Bulletin of Education and Research*. Retrieved from: http://pu.edu.pk/images/journal/ier/PDF-FILES/14_42_3_20.pdf
- Cole, C. (2018). Why teaching second language listening is difficult and how to use bottom-up listening strategies to teach listening more effectively. *CONTACT Magazine*. Retrieved from: <http://contact.teslontario.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/Cole-Listening.pdf>
- Coskun, H. & Köprü, M. U. (2021). An overview of listening skills of secondary school students: barriers and suggestions. *Educational Policy Analysis and Strategic Research*. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1328770.pdf>
- Furwana, Dewi & Syam, Andi. (2021). “Listening is Hard”: ADDIE Model on the Development of English Listening Worksheets. *Language Circle: Journal of Language and Literature*. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/355870412_Listening_is_Hard_ADDIE_Model_on_the_Development_of_English_Listening_Worksheets
- Gearhart, C., Denham, J., & Bodie, Graham. (2014). Listening as a Goal-Directed Activity. *Western Journal of Communication*. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271753713_Listening_as_a_Goal-Directed_Activity
- Gilakjani, A. P., & Sabouri, N. B. (2016). Learners’ Listening Comprehension Difficulties in English Language Learning: A Literature Review. *English Language Teaching*, 9, 123-133. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v9n6p123>
- Haji, B. A. & Saaed, S.A. (2022). The Effects of the Physical Setting on Students’ Listening Comprehension. *International Journal of Language and Literary Studies*. 4(4).39-51. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.36892/ijlls.v4i4.1080>
- Jimenez, H. (2022). Relational Pedagogy: Strategies for effective and sustainable relationships with students. Retrieved from: <https://scholarworks.calstate.edu/downloads/8c97kx90m>
- Kapur, R. (2019). Development of Teaching-Learning Materials. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334083571_Development_of_Teaching-Learning_Materials
- Khoirunnisa, F. (2023). Teaching style used by teachers in a private junior high school in Salatiga. Retrieved from: <https://dspace.uii.ac.id/bitstream/handle/123456789/42658/17322038.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

- Kumar, R. N. & Shankar, L. R. (2021). The importance of listening skill in language acquisition- the problems experienced & strategies adopted in teaching listening skill. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology*. Retrieved from: https://www.ijirt.org/master/publishedpaper/IJIRT151261_PAPER.pdf
- La'biran, E. & Dewi, R. (2021). Exploration of Western Teacher's Style in Teaching Speaking at State Senior High School 2 Rantepao in Toraja Utara- Indonesia. *Multicultural Education*. Retrieved from: <http://ijdri.com/me/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/6.pdf>
- La'biran, R. (2017). A Study on the Western English Teacher Styles in Teaching at the Tenth Grade at SMAN 2 Rantepao. *Jurnal Keguruan Dan Ilmu Pendidikan*, 2(3), 347–357. Retrieved from <https://journals.ukitoraja.ac.id/index.php/jkip/article/view/170>
- Lestari, P. A., Kurniasari, R., & Riznanda, W. A. (2021). Analysing Teacher's Difficulties in Teaching Listening Comprehension. *Jadila: Journal of Development and Innovation in Language and Literature Education*. Retrieved from: <https://ejournal.karinosseff.org/index.php/jadila/article/view/160/152>
- Mazloom, S. & Hussain, M. A. (2020). Identification of Teaching Styles in English Language
- Mulder, P. (2019). Analytical Listening. Retrieved <https://www.toolshero.com/communication-methods/analytical-listening/>
- Nemec, P. B., Spagnolo, A. C., & Soydan, A. S. (2017). Can you hear me now? Teaching listening skills. *Psychiatric Rehabilitation Journal*, 40(4), 415–417. <https://doi.org/10.1037/prj0000287>
- Okume, G. D. (2019). Improving Students' Proficiency in Listening.
- Ostad, Omid & Tarang, Mohammad & Mojdehi, Hamed. (2018). The Effect of Task-Based Listening Activities on the Listening Comprehension: A Case of Iranian IELTS Candidates. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature*. Retrieved from: <https://journals.aiac.org.au/index.php/IJALEL/article/view/4675>
- Putri, S. & Refnaldi (2020). Developing Task Based Language Teaching Worksheet as the Solution in Teaching and Learning English. *Atlantis Press SARL*. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.210914.019>.
- Ridwan, H., Sutresna, I., & Haryeti, P. (2019). Teaching Styles of the Teachers and Learning Styles of the Students. *IOP Publishing*. Retrieved from: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1318/1/012028/pdf>
- Sah, Fauziana & Shah, Parilah. (2020). Teachers' Beliefs and Practices in Teaching Listening. *Creative Education*. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339505374_Teachers'_Beliefs_and_Practices_in_Teaching_Listening
- Salazar, L. R. (2017). The influence of business students' listening styles on their compassion and self-compassion. *SAGE Publication*. Retrieved from: <https://self-compassion.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/Ramos2017.pdf>
- Sarmiento, F. S. (2018). Teacher-made materials focused on significant learning to foster oral interaction. Retrieved from: <https://bdigital.uexternado.edu.co/server/api/core/bitstreams/a5aac99b-b47c-4fd6-8da0-e34c2222124b/content>
- SEAMEO INNOTECH. (2012). K To 12 Toolkit: Resource Guide for Teacher Educators, School Administrators and Teachers. Philippines. Retrieved from: <https://www.seameo-innotech.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/k-12-toolkit.pdf>
- Sengsouliya, S., Soukhavong, S., Phonekeo, S., Sengsouliya, S., & Xaixanith, T., (2021). Mismatches in teachers' teaching and students' learning styles in English classes at a secondary level: A case study of Laotian secondary schools. *International Journal of Research in English Education*. Retrieved from: <https://ijreeonline.com/article-1-433-en.pdf>

- Siedlecki, S.L. (2020). Understanding descriptive research designs and methods. *Clinical Nurse Specialist*, 34(1), 8–12. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1097/NUR.0000000000000493>
- Singhal, M., & Vohra, S. (2011). Importance of Developing Analytical Listening Skills While Teaching English as a Second Language to a Mixed Ability Class. *Learning Community*, 133-138. Retrieved from: <https://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:lco&volume=2&issue=1&article=014>
- Statement on the Philippines' ranking in the 2018 PISA results. Retrieved from: <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2019/12/04/statement-on-the-philippines-ranking-in-the-2018-pisa-results/>
- Tersta, F. W. & Novianti A. (2017). Listening to students' voices: students' problems in listening comprehension. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/316302873_Listening_to_Students_VoiceStudents'_Problems_in_Listening_Comprehension
- Thi, T. T. & Nguyen, T. T. (2021). The Effects of Classroom Management Styles on Students' Motivation and Academic Achievement in Learning English. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*. Retrieved from: <https://www.ijlter.org/index.php/ijlter/article/download/3183/pdf>
- Unver, M. M. (2017). The Use of Authentic Materials with Low-Level Learners of English. *European Journal of English Language Teaching*. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED580820.pdf>
- Wuryaningrum, Rusdhianti & Mutiah, Arju & Rijadi, Arief. (2022). Critical Listening: Teacher Language Awareness (TLA). *The International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Invention*. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359788322_Critical_Listening_Teacher_Language_Awareness_TLA